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The World Wide Web: How a Side Project Changed the Way We Access Information and Interact with Each Other

Marco Aiello (University of Stuttgart, Germany)

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World Wide Web is the name given by Tim Berners-Lee to his creation, which originated as a side project while at CERN. Frustrated with the difficulty of retrieving and organising relevant work information, he decided to create a software system in which information would be represented as entities connected by qualified links. He recalls, “I wrote it in my spare time and for my personal use, and for no loftier reason than to help me remember the connections among the various people, computers, and projects at the lab” [1]. The system soon caught the attention of his colleagues, and Berners-Lee was encouraged to seek institutional support to further develop it. His director at the time, Mike Sendall, famously labelled the project proposal “vague but exciting,” and granted him the necessary resources to pursue it.

What began as a local information management tool at a European research laboratory quickly became a global phenomenon. Within a few years, the World Wide Web evolved from a set of interconnected hypertext documents into the backbone of modern communication and commerce. The release of the first popular browser, Mosaic, in 1993, and later the emergence of Netscape, Microsoft Internet Explorer, and open standards coordinated by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), transformed the Web into a ubiquitous platform. From the early academic pages of universities and research institutes, the Web expanded to host millions of websites, eventually reshaping how societies produce, distribute, and consume

knowledge; while also profoundly changing commerce and even the foundation of social interactions.

Technologically, the Web’s evolution reflects a continuous layering of innovation. The initial Web of information, a system for linking and reading documents, grew into a Web of software and business services, enabling interaction and transaction through protocols and languages such as HTTP, HTML, SOAP, and later REST. This, in turn, enabled e-commerce, online banking, and the emergence of digital economies. In the 2000s, the rise of social platforms and user-generated content led to what is often referred to as the social Web, which fundamentally altered media, education, and politics. Today, Web-based technologies underpin artificial intelligence, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things.

The Web’s societal impact is difficult to overstate. Recent studies estimate that over five billion people, that is, roughly two-thirds of the world’s population, use the Web daily. The economic value created by Web-based services exceeds trillions of euros annually, fuelling industries ranging from education to entertainment, logistics and finance. Yet, none of this was anticipated in Berners-Lee’s original proposal. His goal was not to start a company or create a market, but simply to make knowledge easier to navigate. His motivation was intellectual curiosity and the pursuit of a more elegant way to manage information, not a plan for commercial transformation. The Web’s extraordinary success thus stands as a

compelling validation of Flexner’s argument that freeing research from immediate utility is the most powerful path to societal progress. Furthermore, one can even dig further historically into the impact of basic research on the success of the Web. Similar to what Flexner claimed of Marconi regarding the radio [2, p.5], one could argue that Tim Berners-Lee was inevitable. The Web can be seen as the culmination of a lineage of visionary ideas: Vannevar Bush’s concept of the Memex, a theoretical device for associative information storage; Douglas Engelbart’s onLine System,

which introduced hypertext and interactive computing; and Bill Atkinson’s HyperCard environment for the Macintosh [3]. Each of these contributed essential elements that made the Web conceivable, yet it was Berners-Lee’s curiosity, persistence, and belief in open source that turned them into a reality.

In hindsight, the World Wide Web stands as one of the clearest examples of how basic, curiosity-driven research and creative experimentation, pursued without commercial intent, can profoundly reshape the world [4].

References

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